

Parallelising the Polyphony: High-Performance Algorithms for Music Pattern Matching

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Abstract. We address two fundamental problems in symbolic music pattern matching: (1) exact matching, where all notes of a pattern must align with notes in the dataset, and (2) pattern subset matching, where the goal is to identify all translations of the pattern that yield partial matches based on shared onset-pitch pairs. We propose two new bit-parallel algorithms that solve these problems in $O(n'm(c/w))$ and $O(n'm \log m(c/w))$ time, respectively, where n' is the number of distinct dataset note onset times, m is the number of pattern notes, c is the number of possible pitches and w is the computer word size. In practice, our methods can achieve substantial speedups and require less working space than the previous best-known solutions for these problems, making them well-suited for large-scale music retrieval tasks.

Keywords: Symbolic music retrieval · Pattern matching · Bit-parallelism · Polyphonic music · Geometric representation.

1 Introduction

Content-based music retrieval (CBMR) is a fundamental problem in computational music analysis and information retrieval. As digital music archives expand, efficient CBMR algorithms are increasingly necessary. This paper addresses a specific CBMR task in symbolically encoded music: detecting occurrences of musical patterns in a polyphonic music database.

We focus on symbolic music representations, which provide explicit structure for algorithmic processing, making them particularly well-suited for tasks that require precise note-level matching across large datasets. However, as demonstrated in [5], the boundary between symbolic and audio-based music representations is not rigid. This suggests that methods originally developed for one domain may be transferable to the other.

Unlike textual data, where sequences of symbols can be matched using traditional string algorithms, music retrieval presents additional challenges due to its polyphonic (multi-voiced) nature, especially when combined with approximate matching and translation invariance. The latter is a fundamental requirement in real-world music retrieval: a matching pattern should be identifiable regardless of its position in time or its transposition in pitch.

Fig. 1. Illustration of Ukkonen et al.’s exact pattern matching algorithm [16]. Crosses and white circles represent the query pattern P and the dataset T , respectively. A translation $f = t - p[1]$ aligns P with a subset of T . The resulting match $P + f$ is indicated by white rectangles surrounding the matched dataset points.

Early approaches to symbolic music retrieval relied on string-matching techniques (see, e.g., [2, 4, 7, 12]), some of which employed bit-parallelism [3, 8, 9]. However, these methods scale poorly in complex scenarios involving polyphony and flexible matching conditions. Later work introduced geometric representations of music, allowing more natural treatment of translation-invariant matching and polyphonic textures [10, 11, 14, 15].

Building on this geometric perspective, we propose efficient bit-parallel algorithms for two core symbolic music retrieval problems: one that requires complete matches and the other that allows partial matches. Both formulations support polyphonic patterns and datasets.

Let us now define the two pattern-matching problems considered in this study. We are given a *dataset* T consisting of n note events and a *pattern* P consisting of m note events. Each note event e is a two-dimensional point $(e.x, e.y)$ where $e.x$ denotes the onset time and the $e.y$ denotes the pitch. Multiple events may share the same onset, i.e., the dataset and the pattern may be polyphonic.

A *translation* f is a two-dimensional vector $(f.x, f.y)$ where $f.x$ denotes the time shift and $f.y$ denotes the pitch shift. Given a translation f and a pattern P , the translated pattern is defined as

$$P + f = \{(p.x + f.x, p.y + f.y) \mid p \in P\}. \quad (1)$$

In *exact matching*, the goal is to find all translations f such that $(P + f) \subseteq T$, i.e., the translated pattern appears in the dataset. In *subset matching*, the goal is to find all translations f such that $(P + f) \cap T \neq \emptyset$, i.e., at least one pattern note matches a note in the dataset.

We assume that all pitch values are integers in the range $[0, c - 1]$ where c is a fixed constant (typically $c = 128$ with MIDI note numbers). Under this assumption, any subset of pitch values can be represented as a bit vector that consists of c bits. With computer word size w (typically $w = 64$), $\lceil c/w \rceil$ words suffice to represent any subset of pitch values.

Fig. 2. Illustration of heap-based merging in subset matching. Each query point p_i yields a sorted list of translation vectors f_i (shown in reverse order). The heap repeatedly selects the smallest current f_i across lists and outputs it, revealing repeated vectors. The most frequent vector (here f_3 appears 3 times) indicates the best match.

2 Related Work

2.1 Previous Algorithms

Ukkonen et al. [16] presented simple and efficient algorithms for the exact and subset pattern matching problems. Their algorithms assume that both P and T are represented as lists whose points are lexicographically sorted. In exact matching, a candidate translation $f = t - p[1]$ is computed for each point $t \in T$, aligning the first point $p[1]$ in P with t . The rest of the points in P are then incrementally translated by f and checked for their presence in T (see Fig. 1).

To perform this verification efficiently, the algorithm maintains a set of forward-moving pointers—one for each p in P —that scan T sequentially without backtracking, thanks to the lexicographic ordering. This ensures that every translation candidate is evaluated in amortised constant time per query point. Thus, the worst-case time complexity is $O(nm)$. However, in practical cases where full matches are rare, the expected running time is $O(n)$.

The algorithm for the subset pattern matching problem considers all $O(nm)$ pairwise translation vectors $f = t - p$ for $p \in P$ and $t \in T$. Each translation f represents a potential partial alignment, contributing one vote for aligning p with t . Instead of evaluating each of these candidates in isolation, the algorithm efficiently counts the frequency of each translation vector by sweeping over T in parallel for all $p \in P$. Specifically, it generates m sorted lists of translation vectors, each corresponding to a fixed p , and merges them using a priority queue. During the merge, the frequency of each distinct translation is tracked, and the translation with the highest count (i.e., producing the largest subset match) is selected (see Fig. 2).

The running time of the subset pattern matching algorithm is $O(nm \log m)$, where the logarithmic factor arises from using a priority queue to sort and count the translation frequencies. Once all translations have been processed, the translation yielding the largest intersection size is selected as the optimal translation.

2.2 Bit-Parallelism in Music Retrieval

Bit-parallelism is a computational technique exploiting the parallel processing capabilities of computer processors by using bitwise operations to perform multiple computations simultaneously within a single computer word. Instead of

processing individual elements, multiple values are packed into a word and logical or arithmetic operations are applied in parallel, reducing the number of required operations. This technique is widely used in dynamic programming and string-matching problems (see, e.g. [13]).

In music retrieval, bit-parallelism has been previously applied in cases where music is modelled as strings (sequences of characters). Lemström and Tarhio [9] proposed an efficient approach for searching monophonic patterns within polyphonic target datasets using bitwise operations. Their method extends the shift-or algorithm [1] to handle polyphony by treating notes as sets of symbols rather than as sequential characters. To accommodate transposition invariance, they use an interval-based representation. Their results demonstrate that bit-parallelism significantly accelerates monophonic pattern detection, particularly when the average chord size remains small.

Crochemore et al. [3] introduced a music retrieval approach that combines bit-parallelism with suffix automata for efficient (δ, γ) -matching, where δ and γ represent the maximum allowed deviation between corresponding elements of the pattern and the target dataset, and the total permissible sum of these deviations across the entire pattern.¹ Their experiments demonstrate that their algorithm is particularly effective in cases where large values of δ are permitted.

Lemström et al. [8] applied bit-parallelism to a related problem setting, considering the longest common subsequence (LCS) problem for musical strings under transposition. They developed a bit-parallel approach for transposition-invariant pattern matching using indel distance (insertions and deletions allowed). Their algorithm achieves significant speedups over classical methods, reducing the complexity to $O(w \log m)$, where w is the number of bits in a computer word. They also demonstrate that their algorithm could be extended to δ -matching and, to some extent, to polyphonic music retrieval.

Although bit-parallelism has been utilised for musical pattern matching, previous studies have modelled music as sequences of symbols, which is often limiting in real-world applications. This study is the first to apply bit-parallelism to music retrieval using a geometric representation, offering a more flexible and structurally informed approach to pattern matching in musical data. Our approach addresses the limitations of sequence-based models and provides a scalable solution for efficient pattern retrieval in large symbolic music databases.

3 New Algorithms

This section presents bit-parallel algorithms for the exact pattern matching and pattern subset matching problems. Like in the previous algorithms discussed in the literature, we assume that the dataset and pattern notes are given as sorted lists. The dataset T consists of n note events $t[1], t[2], \dots, t[n]$, and the

¹ A technique allowing minor variations in numeric values. Two values, a and b , are considered equivalent if $|a - b| \leq \delta$, where δ is the predefined tolerance and γ is the allowed total sum of differences.

Fig. 3. Illustration of bit-parallelism improving search efficiency. Left: a piano-roll representation of a real excerpt (Sibelius' Kuusi). Right: the same excerpt, where notes with the same onset time are grouped in boxes, each encoded as single bit vector. Unlike Ukkonen et al. [16], which computes shift vectors separately for each point, our method processes all shifts affecting the same bit vector in one step. For instance, instead of 28 shift computations for the first note, our approach requires only 10. The position of a group is indicated by the label below the box.

pattern P consists of m note events $p[1], p[2], \dots, p[m]$. The events are sorted lexicographically primarily by onset time and secondarily by pitch.

The reduced time and space requirements of the bit-parallel algorithms are based on the fact that translations targeting notes with the same onset time can be computed in a single bit-parallel operation (see Fig. 3).

3.1 Dataset Conversion and Bit Operations

The first step in our algorithms is to preprocess the dataset so that the note events are converted to bit vectors. We create a bit vector for each onset time with at least one note event. Each bit vector contains information about all note events having that onset time.

Each bit vector has a fixed length of c before processing the dataset. Typically, c is a power of two, and it is assumed that each pitch in the dataset is an integer between 0 and $c - 1$. In many applications, a good choice for c is $2^7 = 128$ because each MIDI note number is an integer between 0 and 127.

Consider a specific onset time with s note events with pitches b_1, b_2, \dots, b_s . To store these note events, we create a bit vector with bit 1 in positions b_1, b_2, \dots, b_s and bit 0 in all other positions. For example, if $c = 8$ and the active pitches are 1, 2 and 5, the resulting bit vector is 00100110. Note that the bit vector positions are indexed from right to left.

We represent the converted dataset as n' pairs

$$t'[1], t'[2], \dots, t'[n']$$

where n' is the number of distinct onset times in the original dataset. The first element of each pair is the onset time, and the second element is the bit vector. The pairs are ordered by the onset times in increasing order. Creating the bit vectors takes $O(n)$ time.

Algorithm 1 Exact pattern matching algorithm

```

1: for  $i = 1$  to  $n'$  do
2:    $q[1] = i$ 
3:   Update pointers  $q[2], \dots, q[m]$ 
4:    $mask = t'[i].y$ 
5:   for  $j = 2$  to  $m$  do
6:     if  $t'[q[j]].x - t'[q[1]].x = p[j].x - p[1].x$  then
7:        $d = p[j].y - p[j - 1].y$ 
8:        $mask = \text{shift}(mask, d)$ 
9:        $mask = mask$  and  $t'[w[j]].y$ 
10:    else
11:       $mask = 0$ 
12:    end if
13:  end for
14:  Report  $\text{bitcount}(mask)$  patterns
15: end for

```

For example, suppose that the original dataset contains the following events:

$$(1, 0), (1, 4), (1, 7), (4, 0), (4, 5), (6, 0), (6, 4), (6, 7)$$

There are three distinct onset times 1, 4 and 6, which means that we create three bit vectors. Assuming $c = 8$, the converted dataset is as follows:

$$t'_1 = (1, 10010001), \quad t'_2 = (4, 00100001), \quad t'_3 = (6, 10010001).$$

In practice, we can present the bit vectors more compactly as integers. For example, the bit vector 10010001 corresponds to the integer 145.

There are two benefits of converting the dataset into bit vectors. First, the number of distinct onsets (n') can be much smaller than that of all note events (n) because of the polyphony. Second, we can use efficient bit operations to handle all notes with the same onset time simultaneously.

We can use the bit shifts $v \ll d$ (left bit shift) and $v \gg d$ (right bit shift) to move each pitch in the bit vector v by d steps higher or lower, respectively. We will use the syntax $\text{shift}(v, d)$ to denote a left bit shift by d steps if d is nonnegative and a right bit shift by $-d$ steps if d is negative.

The operation a *and* b creates a bit vector with pitches that appear in a and b . The operation a *or* b creates a bit vector with pitches that appear in either a , b , or both. Finally, the bit count operation calculates the number of active pitches in a bit vector.

The above bit operations work in $O(c/w)$ time, where c is the bit vector length and w is the computer word size. In practice, the operations are very efficient if c is relatively small.

3.2 Exact Pattern Matching

Consider an exact pattern occurrence

$$t[i_1], t[i_2], \dots, t[i_m]$$

before conversion. We know that

$$t[i_{k+1}] - t[i_k] = p[k + 1] - p[k]$$

for each $k = 1, 2, \dots, m-1$, because both the onset time and the pitch differences must match.

In the converted dataset, there are m events

$$t'[i'_1], t'[i'_2], \dots, t'[i'_m]$$

where

$$t'[i'_k].x = t[i_k].x$$

and $t'[i'_k].y$ has bit 1 in position $t[i_k].y$, for each $k = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Note that only the dataset and not the pattern is converted, and the number of pattern note events is still m .

Consider, for example, an exact match in the original dataset that contains the notes

$$(1, 2), (2, 9), (3, 6)$$

In the converted dataset, this match corresponds to a match

$$(1, v_1), (2, v_2), (3, v_3)$$

where v_1, v_2 and v_3 have bit 1 in positions 2, 9 and 6, respectively.

Using bit-parallelism, we can simultaneously consider *all* pattern occurrences whose first note aligns with the same onset time in the dataset. For example, to continue the previous example, there could be another match

$$(1, 4), (2, 11), (3, 8)$$

in the original dataset. This match corresponds to the same match in the converted dataset, with the difference that v_1, v_2 and v_3 have bit 1 in positions 4, 11 and 8, respectively.

We can create a bit-parallel algorithm that uses bit operations to track patterns with a specific onset time pattern. For each $i = 1, 2, \dots, n'$, we report the patterns whose first note has the onset time $t'[i].x$. We use the pointer technique discussed in [16] to efficiently locate the bit vectors corresponding to the pattern's onsets. We use m pointers, one for each pattern note, that point to the dataset. During the algorithm, we repeatedly move the pointers to the right to discover the pattern occurrences. We start with the bit vector $t'[i].y$ and modify the bit vector using bit shifts according to the pitch differences. The *and* operation filters the patterns during the search, and the bit count operation is finally used to count the total number of patterns.

Algorithm 2 Pattern subset matching algorithm

```

1: Create a priority queue  $Q$ 
2: for  $j = 1$  to  $m$  do
3:   Add subset identifier for  $(1, j)$  to  $Q$ 
4: end for
5: while  $Q$  is not empty do
6:   Fetch a subset identifier group  $g$  from  $Q$ 
7:   Update the subset identifiers in  $Q$ 
8:    $mask = 0$ 
9:   for each bit vector  $v$  in  $g$  do
10:     $mask = mask$  or  $v$ 
11:   end for
12:   Report  $bitcount(mask)$  patterns
13: end while

```

Algorithm 1 presents the implementation in pseudocode: The m pointers, $q[1], q[2], \dots, q[m]$, each move $O(n')$ steps during the search, which means that we can locate all bit vectors in $O(n'm)$ time. The bit shifts, *and* operations and bit count operations work in $O(c/w)$ time, meaning that the algorithm's overall time complexity is $O(n'm(c/w))$.

3.3 Pattern Subset Matching

Consider a pattern subset match

$$t[i_1], t[i_2], \dots, t[i_s]$$

that corresponds to a pattern subset

$$p[j_1], p[j_2], \dots, p[j_s]$$

of size s where

$$1 \leq j_1 < j_2 < \dots < j_s \leq m.$$

In this case, the point

$$t[i_k] - (p[j_k] - p[1])$$

is the same point for each $k = 1, 2, \dots, s$ and we call this the *subset identifier point* of the pattern subset occurrence. By using subset identifier points, we can discover partial patterns that do not necessarily include the first pattern note. If the subset includes the first pattern note, the subset identifier point is the dataset note where the pattern occurrence begins. If the subset does not include the first pattern note, the subset identifier point is the position that the first pattern note *would* have in the dataset in an exact occurrence.

Let us consider an example where the dataset is $T = \{(4, 5), (6, 4)\}$ and the pattern is $P = \{(1, 1), (2, 2), (3, 3), (4, 1)\}$. This dataset contains the pattern subset

$$(2, 2), (4, 1)$$

Work	Note events	Bit vectors	Patterns
Symphony 1	40,240	30,880	41,114
Symphony 2	51,259	39,498	52,341
Symphony 3	56,012	14,571	69,399
Symphony 4	38,807	13,440	46,379
Symphony 5	36,329	8,866	48,074
Symphony 6	39,470	13,471	47,534
Symphony 7	50,368	11,809	62,536
Symphony 8	51,423	39,368	51,487
Symphony 9	88,434	19,507	121,706

Table 1. Dataset overview.

that consists of the 2nd and 4th pattern note. The subset identifier point is

$$(4, 5) - ((2, 2) - (1, 1)) = (3, 4)$$

which equals to

$$(6, 4) - ((4, 1) - (1, 1)) = (3, 4).$$

This would be the first pattern point in the exact pattern occurrence

$$(3, 4), (4, 5), (5, 6), (6, 4).$$

To find all maximal pattern subsets, we can consider all pairs of the form (i, j) where i points to the dataset and j points to the pattern. For each such pair, we calculate the subset identifier point

$$t[i] - (p[j] - p[1]).$$

Two pairs (i_1, j_1) and (i_2, j_2) belong to the same pattern subset exactly when they have the same subset identifier point. Thus, we can find the subsets by grouping the subset identifier points. Since the onset times in the dataset are already sorted, an efficient way to do this is to use a priority queue to merge m lists of n subset identifier points [16].

We can extend this idea to bit vectors and work with the converted dataset. Instead of subset identifier points with single pitch values, we use subset identifiers that contain bit vectors. We consider all pairs of the form (i, j) , where i refers to the converted dataset and j refers to the pattern. For each such pair, we create a pair

$$(t'[i].x - (p[j].x - p[1].x), \text{mask})$$

where

$$\text{mask} = \text{shift}(t'[i].y, p[1].y - p[j].y).$$

After creating the subset identifiers, we can process them in groups. Each group of subset identifiers corresponds to h patterns where h is the total number of bit positions with bit 1 in at least one bit vector.

Work	A1 [16]	B1 (Proposed)	A2 [16]	B2 (Proposed)
Symphony 1	6.3	4.2	241.7	219.2
Symphony 2	13.0	9.0	374.1	323.9
Symphony 3	32.7	5.8	641.7	135.9
Symphony 4	12.9	2.9	266.6	75.9
Symphony 5	24.5	3.9	497.1	90.9
Symphony 6	11.3	2.6	241.3	66.0
Symphony 7	24.9	4.2	491.7	89.6
Symphony 8	14.2	10.0	360.9	321.3
Symphony 9	94.7	13.0	1963.1	308.2

Table 2. Running times (s) for the exact (A1, B1) and subset (A2, B2) pattern matching algorithms. A1 and A2 are those of Ukkonen et al. [16]; B1 and B2 are those of the proposed methods.

Algorithm 2 shows the pseudocode for the bit-parallel algorithm. It maintains a priority queue containing m elements, each representing a subset identifier for a specific pattern position. The algorithm discovers each subset identifier group using the priority queue and counts the number of patterns using the *or* and bit count operations. The algorithm works in $O(n'm \log(m)(c/w))$ time.

Note a subtle implementation detail. While note pitches lie between 0 and $c - 1$, an identifier may have a pitch outside this range. We can either restrict identifiers to this range or ignore such subsets.

4 Experiments and Results

We implemented the algorithms discussed in this paper in C++. We implemented the algorithms to report the number of pattern occurrences and utilise the GCC `__int128` data type for storing the bit vectors. Our implementations are available on GitHub².

We conducted experiments using a dataset of Beethoven’s symphonies 1–9. Table 1 shows an overview of the dataset. We converted each work from MIDI files to point sets. To create the patterns, we collected all distinct patterns of 10 successive note events from each MIDI track. These patterns were used to measure the running time of the algorithms. We conducted the tests in a Linux environment on a computer with an Intel Core i5-10210U processor.

Table 2 shows the results of the exact pattern matching algorithms. Algorithm A1 corresponds to the original exact matching algorithm [16], and B1 is our new bit-parallel algorithm. The total running time for processing all pattern queries is shown in seconds. The new bit-parallel algorithm is more efficient in all tests. The most significant differences are in symphonies 3–7 and 9, where the number of bit vectors is small compared to the number of all note events.

Table 2 shows the results of the pattern subset matching algorithms. Algorithm A2 corresponds to the original subset matching algorithm [16], and B2 is

² <https://github.com/c-brahms/parallel-matching>

our new bit-parallel algorithm. The total running time in seconds for processing all pattern queries is shown for each work. The results are similar to those of exact pattern matching: the bit-parallel algorithm is more efficient in all works, and again the most significant differences are in symphonies 3–7 and 9.

In all algorithm implementations, we preprocess the input by sorting the note events. In bit-parallel implementations, we also construct the bit vectors after the sorting process. The preprocessing times are included in the reported running times of the algorithms.

These results demonstrate that the use of bit-parallelism can lead to significant speedups when real datasets and patterns are employed. In general, the larger the polyphony in the database, the greater the advantage of using bit operations. In our dataset, the maximum ratio of the number of note events and bit vectors is 4.53 in Symphony 9. In this case, the ratio of running times of A1 and B1 is 7.28, and the ratio of running times of A2 and B2 is 6.37. Thus, the difference in running times is even larger than the difference in the number of dataset events. A possible explanation is that the algorithms B1 and B2 are more cache-friendly due to the reduced dataset size.

5 Conclusions

In this paper, we have introduced two new bit-parallel algorithms for solving fundamental music pattern matching problems in symbolic polyphonic music: exact pattern matching and pattern subset matching. Building on a geometric representation of music data, our approach combines structural awareness of music with the computational efficiency of bit-level operations. By converting polyphony into a series of bit vectors, our algorithms efficiently perform parallelised pitch comparisons.

Our bit-parallel algorithms solve the exact matching problem in $O(n'm(c/w))$ time and the subset matching problem in $O(n'm \log m(c/w))$ time, where n' is the number of distinct onset times in the dataset notes, m is the number of pattern notes, c is the number of possible pitches, and w is the computer word size. The previous best algorithms for these problems operate in $O(nm)$ and $O(nm \log m)$ time, respectively, where n represents the total number of note events in the dataset. In practice, n' can be significantly smaller than n , and typically $c = 128$, in which case our new algorithms clearly outperform the previous ones.

Our algorithms could be extended to report, for example, the starting position of each pattern or the number of notes in each subset. This could be done in $O(nm)$ additional time by using bit operations to extract the positions that have ones in the bit vectors and doing some extra bookkeeping.

If we assume that the onset times are integers, it could be possible to implement the subset pattern matching algorithm more efficiently by using a faster sorting method, such as a variation of the counting sort algorithm. By using such an implementation, the time complexity would not include a logarithmic factor, making it a practical optimisation.

Future work will explore applying bit-parallelism with stronger timing invariances, such as time-scaling and time-warping invariances (see, e.g., [6]), thereby enabling greater flexibility in music retrieval scenarios.

References

1. Baeza-Yates, R., Gonnet, G.H.: A new approach to text searching. *Commun. ACM* **35**(10), 74–82 (1992)
2. Crawford, T.: String matching techniques for musical similarity and melodic recognition. *Computing in Musicology* **11**, 73–100 (1998)
3. Crochemore, M., Iliopoulos, C.S., Navarro, G., Pinzon, Y.J., Reid, J.F.: A bit-parallel suffix automaton approach for (δ, γ) -matching in music retrieval. In: *Proc. Int. Symp. on String Proc. and Inf. Retr. (SPIRE)*. LNCS, vol. 2857, pp. 211–223 (2003)
4. Ghias, A., Logan, J., Chamberlin, D., Smith, B.: Query by humming - musical information retrieval in an audio database. In: *ACM Multimedia*. pp. 231–236 (1995)
5. Laaksonen, A., Lemström, K.: On finding symbolic themes directly from audio files using dynamic programming. In: *Proc. Int. Soc. for Music Inf. Retr. Conf. (ISMIR)*. pp. 47–52 (2013)
6. Laaksonen, A., Lemström, K.: Advanced polyphonic music pattern matching algorithms with timing invariances. In: *Proc. Math. and Comp. in Music (MCM)*. p. 242–254. LNCS (2024)
7. Lemström, K.: *String Matching Techniques for Music Retrieval*. Ph.D. thesis, University of Helsinki (2000)
8. Lemström, K., Navarro, G., Pinzon, Y.: Practical algorithms for transposition-invariant string-matching. *Journal of Discrete Algorithms* **3**(2), 267–292 (2005)
9. Lemström, K., Tarhio, J.: Searching monophonic patterns within polyphonic sources. In: *Proc. Int. Conf. on Computer-Assisted Inf. Retr. (RIA0'00)*. pp. 1261–1279 (2000)
10. Lubiw, A., Tanur, L.: Pattern matching in polyphonic music as a weighted geometric translation problem. In: *Proc. Int. Conf. on Music Inf. Retr. (ISMIR)*. p. 289–296 (2004)
11. Meredith, D., Lemström, K., Wiggins, G.: Algorithms for discovering repeated patterns in multidimensional representations of polyphonic music. *Journal of New Music Research* **31**(4), 321–345 (2002)
12. Mongeau, M., Sankoff, D.: Comparison of musical sequences. *Computers and Humanities* **24**, 161–175 (1990)
13. Myers, G.: A fast bit-vector algorithm for approximate string matching based on dynamic programming. *Journal of the ACM* **46**(3), 395–415 (1999)
14. Romming, C.A., Selfridge-field, E.: Algorithms for polyphonic music retrieval: the Hausdorff metric and geometric hashing. In: *Proc. Int. Conf. on Music Inf. Retr. (ISMIR)*. pp. 457–462 (2007)
15. Typke, R., Giannopoulos, P., Veltkamp, R.C., Wiering, F., Van Oostrum, R.: Using transportation distances for measuring melodic similarity. In: *Proc. Int. Soc. for Music Inf. Retr. Conf. (ISMIR)*. pp. 107–114 (2003)
16. Ukkonen, E., Lemström, K., Mäkinen, V.: Geometric algorithms for transposition invariant content based music retrieval. In: *Proc. Int. Soc. for Music Inf. Retr. Conf. (ISMIR)*. pp. 193–199 (2003)